

211 (4.5), 276 (4.10) and 347 (4.2); λ_{\max} (MeOH + AlCl₃ + HCl) (log ϵ) 211 (3.92), 278 (3.88) and 329 (4.05) indicative of 2 adjacent OH groups; δ (DMSO-d₆) 6.19 (1H, d, *J* 10 Hz, H-3), 6.7 (1H, d, *J* 8 Hz, H-5), 6.8 (1H, d, *J* 8 Hz, H-6), 7.9 (1H, d, *J* 9 Hz, H-4), 9.27 (1H, br s, D₂O exchangeable), 9.8 (1H, br s, D₂O exchangeable). The above data were in agreement with those reported for daphnetin⁵. There appears to be no report on the occurrence of daphnetin dimethyl ether, hydrangetin, daphnetin-7-methyl ether and daphnetin in *Eupatorium* species.

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Flavonol Glycosides from the Leaves of *Sterculia urens* Roxb.

BEHMEEDA KHATOON, MD. KHABIRUDDIN,
M. ASIF and W.H. ANSARI*

Department of Chemistry, Aligarh Muslim University,
Aligarh-202 002

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EARLIER work on *Sterculia* revealed the presence of 6-oxygenated flavone derivatives¹⁻³, but recent work on *S. urens*⁴ showed only a C-methyl chalcone which tempted us to reinvestigate this work. We report here the isolation and characterisation of two flavonol diglycosides, quercetin-3-*O*-(6''-*O*- α -L-rhamnopyranosyl)- β -D-glucoside and kaempferol-3-*O*-(6''-*O*- α -L-rhamnopyranosyl)- β -D-glucoside along with four non-flavonoidic compounds. The presence of flavonol rhamnoglucoside is the first example in *Sterculia* genus (Sterculiaceae). The occurrence of flavonol diglycosides in the plant may serve as a useful taxonomic marker.

The dark gummy concentrate of the methanol extract of air-dried leaves (collected from Botanical Garden, Qila, Aligarh) was fractionated into petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°), benzene and water.

The greenish mass obtained from petrol and benzene extracts upon chromatography (Si-gel) and elution with petrol–benzene (9 : 1, 1 : 1) and benzene–EtOAc (9 : 1, 1 : 1) yielded four compounds which were identified as 3-acetyl- β -amyirin, β -amyirin, β -sitosterol and ester of terephthalic acid by spectral studies and comparison with authentic samples.

The brown mass (3 g) obtained from the water extract upon column chromatography (Si-gel) and elution with chloroform–methanol (4 : 1) and preparative pc (Whatman no. 3, n-BuOH–HOAc–H₂O, 4 : 1 : 5) yielded two flavonoids, compounds A (*R_f* 0.45, 300 mg) and B (*R_f* 0.54, 200 mg).

Compound-A ; R=OH
Compound-B ; R=H

Compound A : Compound A, as yellow needle shaped crystals (MeOH), m.p. 188–89°, on hydrolysis with 8% HCl afforded quercetin (m.p., m.m.p., co-tlc and uv spectra) and two sugars, D-glucose (*R_f* 0.18) and L-rhamnose (*R_f* 0.36) (pc, Whatman no. 1, n-BuOH–HOAc–H₂O, 6 : 1 : 2 ; *R_f*, co-pc and colour developed with aniline hydrogen phthalate found identical with authentic sugars). On partial hydrolysis with 1% H₂SO₄ for 1 h, it yielded only L-rhamnose as the sugar (pc) and a yellow compound, m.p. 235–37° showing the rhamnose as terminal sugar. The yellow compound on further hydrolysis (enzymic, emulsin from almond at 35–40° for 70 h or acidic 8% HCl) gave quercetin and D-glucose. The release of D-glucose by emulsin hydrolysis suggested its β -configuration in the linkage. Permethylolation of compound A followed by hydrolysis (HOAc–HCl–H₂O, 7 : 3 : 10) yielded quercetin 5,7,3',4'-tetramethyl ether, m.p. 194°, 2,3,4-tri-*O*-methyl-L-rhamnose (*R_f* 0.75) identified by chromatographic method⁵. The release of these partially methylated sugars suggested the pyranose conformations of the two sugar moieties. The partially methylated aglycone showed characteristic bathochromic shift of 60 nm in band-I with AlCl₃ confirming C-3 glycosylation⁶ in compound A. ¹H nmr spectrum (CDCl₃) of compound A–acetate, m.p. 136°, showed signals at δ 2.30–2.45 due to four phenolic and at δ 1.92–2.15 for six alcoholic acetoxy groups, suggesting it to be a diglycoside. A multiplet centered at δ 0.91 and a doublet at δ 4.52 (*J* 2 Hz) were ascribed to rhamnose

methyl and rhamnose C-1 proton (H-1''). The low J value (J 2 Hz) was due to equatorial-equatorial coupling with H-2'' showing its α -configuration. The anomeric proton of glucose (H-1'') appeared as a doublet at δ 5.35 (J 7 Hz), the large coupling constant being due to *trans*-diaxial coupling with H-2'' suggesting its β -configuration. The above statement was also supported by ^{13}C nmr spectral (DMSO d_6) data. Compound A was thus assigned the structure of quercetin-3-*O*-(6''-*O*- α -L-rhamnopyranosyl)- β -D-glucopyranoside.

Compound B: Compound B, as yellow needles (MeOH), m.p. 153–55°, on hydrolysis with 8% HCl yielded kaempferol (m.p., m.m.p., co-tlc and uv spectra) and two sugars as D-glucose and L-rhamnose (pc). Partial and enzymic hydrolysis as described in compound A, established that the sugars were in disaccharide form with rhamnose as the terminal sugar and D-glucose linked to kaempferol with β -configuration. Permethylation of the compound B followed by Killiani's hydrolysis gave kaempferol 5,7,4'-trimethyl ether, 2,3,4-tri-*O*-methyl-D-glucose and 2,3,4-tri-*O*-methyl-L-rhamnose. The partially methylated aglycone showed a bathochromic shift of 61 nm in band-I with AlCl_3 confirming its C-3 glycosylation⁶. ^1H nmr spectral data of compound B-acetate, m.p. 91°, also supported the above facts. Compound B was thus characterised as kaempferol-3-*O*-(6''-*O*- α -L-rhamnopyranosyl)- β -D-glucopyranoside.

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Chemical Investigation of Stem Bark of *Ficus religiosa* and *Prosopis spicigera*

K. D. SWAMI, G. S. MALIK and N. P. S. BISHI*

Department of Chemistry, J V College, Baraut-250 611

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FICUS religiosa Linn.¹ (Moraceae) and *Prosopis spicigera* Linn.² (Leguminosae) are extensively used in the indigenous system of medicine, A hy-

poglycemic response was reported for β -sitosterol-D-glucoside obtained from the bark of *F. religiosa*³. In continuation to our earlier work⁴ on *F. religiosa*, the present communication deals with the chemical investigation of the bark of the title plants.

The shade dried coarsely powdered stem-bark of both the plants were soxhleted with petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°) for 24 h. The extract was concentrated under reduced pressure and chromatographed over silica gel. The elution was carried out with petroleum ether and its mixture with benzene, furnishing the following compounds.

Ficus religiosa Linn.: Elution with petroleum ether-benzene (9 : 1) afforded a yellow viscous oil; decomposed on heating above 100°; density, 0.96 at 30°; positive colour reaction for quinone⁵. It was identified as vitamin K₁ by ir⁶, pmr and mass⁷ spectral data and degradation reactions.

The petroleum ether-benzene (3 : 1) eluate yielded white crystals ($\text{Me}_2\text{CO}-\text{C}_6\text{H}_6$), m.p. 81–82°, $\text{C}_{28}\text{H}_{58}\text{O}$ (M^+ 410); ν_{max} (KBr) 3 420, 1 040 (OH) and 725 cm^{-1} [$-(\text{CH}_2)_n-$, $n \geq 4$]. It was identified as n-octacosanol by pmr and mass fragmentation pattern; the acetate, m.p. 65°; the iodide, m.p. 59°.

Petroleum ether-benzene (1 : 1) eluate afforded colourless crystals (EtOH), m.p. 202–03°; $\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{40}\text{O}_8$ (M^+ 470); positive Liebermann-Burchard (L-B) and TNM tests. It was identified as methyl oleanolate by ir, pmr and mass spectral data and further confirmed by hydrolysis to oleanolic acid, m.p. 312–13°; identical pmr and mass spectra with authentic sample and acetate, m.p. 225–26°.

Elution with petroleum ether-benzene (1 : 3) gave white crystals ($\text{MeOH}-\text{Me}_2\text{CO}$), m.p. 141–42°; positive L-B and TNM tests. The ir, pmr and mass spectral data identified it as lanosterol, further confirmed by m.m.p., co-tlc, preparation of the acetate, m.p. 132–33° and the acetate dibromide, m.p. 170–71°.

The petroleum ether-benzene (1 : 5) fraction yielded colourless plates (MeOH), m.p. 138°; positive L-B and TNM tests, the acetate, m.p. 121–22°. It was identified as β -sitosterol by its superimposable ir, m.m.p., co-tlc with an authentic specimen. Further elution with petroleum ether-benzene (1 : 5) gave colourless needles ($\text{C}_6\text{H}_6-\text{MeOH}$), m.p. 171–72°; positive L-B and TNM tests. Spectral data identified it as stigmaterol and further confirmed by m.m.p., co-tlc with authentic sample, the acetate, m.p. 143–44° and the benzoate, m.p. 158–59°.

The benzene-acetone (1 : 1) eluate afforded colourless crystals (MeOH), m.p. 167–68°; positive L-B and TNM tests. The ir, pmr and mass spectral analyses and the hydrazone, m.p. 340–41°, identified it as lupen-3-one.

Prosopis spicigera Linn.: The petroleum ether-benzene (9 : 1) eluate yielded the yellow viscous oil, identical in all respects with vitamin K₁. Elution with petroleum ether-benzene (3 : 1) furnished